

Content Analysis of Abstracts of Business Administration and Management Sciences Theses

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Thesis, Dissertation, Abstract, Content Analysis, Management Sciences, HEC Thesis Repository.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5781178</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this descriptive research is to primarily analyze theses/dissertations abstracts in the field of Business Administration and Management Sciences in Pakistan. The researchers employed quantitative content analysis as their research technique. The researchers searched Pakistan's Higher Education Commission's (the HEC) research repository and located 281 theses in the broader field of business education, afterwards they selected some 96 theses through an iterative process of categorizing those 281 theses into various sub-fields within business education. The findings show that PhD research is often tried and tested in terms of paradigm, research approach, research design, data collection methods and data analysis. A typical thesis in Business Administration and Management Sciences is likely to be formulaic with these distinct features: it will be written by a male, in a five chapter format monograph, approximately 250 pages long, adhering to positivism as its philosophy, deductive in its approach, quantitative in its methodology, using an adapted survey instrument to collect data from respondents, while relying on descriptive statistics, correlation and regression as its data analysis techniques to arrive at some mundane findings and recommendations.</i></p>

Introduction

The colleges, institutes and universities offering Business Administration and Management Sciences programs have mushroomed in Pakistan. In early 1980s there were only a few business schools in the entire country. The mushrooming phenomenon got tremendous impetus once private sector was allowed to operate in higher education field. The private sector soon tapped into the demand for business education. Unlike medical and engineering schools, the establishment of business and management sciences programs do not require lots of initial investment in the infrastructure and labs, thus making them financially attractive for private investments looking for immediate return on investments.

The overwhelming growth in Business Administration and Management Sciences programs precipitated demand for a qualified faculty pool; which in turn made a PhD in Business Administration and Management Sciences a desired terminal degree for people pursuing a career in academia. The Pakistan's Higher Education Commission [the HEC] regulations now require a PhD degree as a prerequisite for someone to get promoted to an Associate Professor level and soon the same will be demanded for the level of Assistant Professor's position (HEC..n.d.). Consequently, a boom in people pursuing a PhD in Business Administration and Management Sciences can be noticed as only three universities in Islamabad awarded 80 PhD degree in a matter of few years (HEC., 2019).

Mostly these new doctors were either already part of the academia or had been joining academia after completing their PhDs. It could not be overemphasized that the quality of their PhD education will ultimately bear upon on the quality of academic departments that they would eventually be affiliated with. Quality in Business Administration and Management sciences' doctorate program is also important as many of these successful candidates would later become supervisors, thus impacting quality of higher education in the field for a long run. Therefore, the overarching purpose of the study is to lay bare the state of art of Business Administration and Management Sciences theses by evaluating primarily their abstracts and some allied objective data from theses and their context.

There are many repositories on internet. Often these repositories catalogue research articles, conceptual papers, empirical studies, dissertations and theses on the basis of their abstracts. Thus, abstracts are regarded as an important section of any research document for assessing the relevance of research during information retrieval phase of the research process. Researchers often use the inclusion/exclusion criteria to bound the scope of their searches. The main document, which serves as the litmus test for this inclusion/exclusion criteria, is often the abstract of a research document. Hence, the importance of the abstract can hardly be overestimated (APA, 2009). Consequently, how to write an abstract and what to include in an abstract are both becoming increasingly standardized as journals, data-bases and universities and other research

producing organizations all have their recommendations on style, length and content of abstracts (Conboy, 2007; Ickes, 2010).

This research is primarily archival in nature but quantitative in its approach as it attempts to lay out the state of art of thesis/dissertation research in Business Administration and Management Sciences in the country by evaluating an important section; an abstract, of PhD education's single most important tangible product that is a PhD thesis itself. It uses quantitative content analysis as its research design and supplemented some theses' affiliated contextual data to support the objectives of the study.

Literature Review

Content analysis is an appropriate method for identifying and describing the state of art in various fields especially when they are in their formative stage (Lockstone-Binney, 2018; Vierula, Stolt, Salminen, Leino-Kilpi & Tuomi, 2016). We believe PhD research in Business Administration and Management Sciences in Pakistan is also one such blooming field as it practically appeared on the scene 15 years back and ever since it has been expanding. We feel it is high time that someone looks into these research in the field by doing abstract analysis first. For instance, in a review of dissertation abstracts of self-directed learning between 1966 to 1991, Long located only seven dissertations that directly or indirectly addressed the elderly (Long, 1993). By evaluating those seven dissertations' abstracts, Long managed to answer his remaining two research questions concerning implications of the research and his conclusions that self-directed learning seems to be positively correlated with life satisfaction and achievement in a few life-skill areas, which were researched in the study (Long, 1993).

In 2001, Jack, Stephens and Evans conducted a study by initially creating a bank of all dissertations regarding 'management of quality' for the period 1981 to 1998. Eventually, 523 abstracts were evaluated by extracting data for only 4 classes of facts: categories, data collection methods, data analysis methods and academic discipline for statistical analysis purposes (Jack et al., 2001). Their study relied on abstracts for drawing conclusions regarding those dissertations like the current study does instead of evaluating the entire theses like the previously mentioned studies did.

Likewise, a study by Stefanos Mantzoukas (2009) published in International Journal of Nursing Studies did quantitative content analysis; which to us appeared to be the same as qualitative analysis in the above mentioned two preceding studies. He did content analysis of all research articles published between 2000 and 2006 in the top 10 nursing journals to see what recommendations can be made for streamlining research to a point, where published articles would become an authentic source for practice (Mantzoukas, 2009). Evidently, it was a step taken in the realm of research for the sake of facilitating evidence-based practice in the nursing field. Like other before him, Mantzoukas (2009) also used abstracts' extracted quantitative data out of those published studies for his analysis (2009).

A 2016 study by Vierula et al., evaluated nursing education research in Finland by reviewing doctoral dissertations between the years 1979-2014. According to them, the data were analyzed by both deductive and inductive content analysis methods; the deductive categories were drawn from literature and later inductive categories emerged from their comparative coding scheme (Vierula et al., 2016). We experienced a similar phenomenon as we started off in our current study with some codes drawn deductively from the literature. Afterwards, once our work proceeded, several sub-categories emerged out of the data inductively just as Vierula et al. (2016) must have experienced. After evaluating 51 dissertations, they identified four areas, where Finnish nursing education research was primarily concentrated with the central focus on learning, mostly students were study informants, surveys followed by interviews were preferred data collection techniques, and findings were congruent with international research in the same field (Vierula et al., 2016).

Another study in the same year by Rajkumar, Kavin, Luo, & Stentoft, (2016) conducted a detailed analysis of 150 Scandinavian doctoral dissertations in logistics and supply chain management (SCM) produced between 2009 to 2014. They discovered a trend that in Scandinavian countries more and more dissertations were collection of articles than monographs unlike our findings, which was an exact opposite of that of theirs. They further catalogued a decreased emphasis on philosophy in those dissertations and we discovered a predominant adherence to just one philosophy. Moreover, they discovered an increasing number of dissertations on inter-organizational SCM issues were noticed, a change from a researched company focus to functional aspects and SCM general research was also recorded (Rajkumar et al., 2016).

Leonie Lockstone-Binney in her 2018 study evaluated abstracts of 41 PhD theses granted by Australian universities from 1995 to 2015 in the field of event studies. Though, similar studies on published articles had been done prior to her work but she felt in order to evaluate the alleged maturity of event studies as a field, one must analyze theses produced in the emerging field. In fact, her content analysis indicates rudimentary coalescence of event-specific knowledge and discipline integration of event studies with sociology acting as the dominant discipline influencing and informing the theses produced in the 20-year studied period (Lockstone-Binney, 2018).

In yet another study covering the period of 2006 to 2016, researchers attempted to see the commonalities and differences between Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) and the Doctor of

Philosophy's (PhD) dissertations in business by utilizing content analysis (MacLennan, Pina, & Gibbons, 2018). The researchers used statistical methods to see if DBA and PhD dissertations in business differ significantly in terms of research methodology, sample size, research type, and by Carnegie classification.

For their research objectives, they located 147 DBA and 151 PhD dissertations produced during the aforementioned period. Final analysis yielded a significant group mean difference in terms of PhD versus DBA dissertations produced in institutions with having an R1 classification by the Carnegie Commission on Higher Education. However, in terms of methodological choice, sample size, or research type (applied vs. basic), based on the degree type that is DBA vs. PhD, neither any significant correlations nor group mean differences were found (MacLennan et al., 2018).

In their recent study published in 2019, Wynstra, Suurmond, & Nullmeier proposes the Purchasing and Supply Management (PSM) is in fact a multidisciplinary field encapsulating "E Pluribus Unum", thus challenging the implicit assumption of many studies that PSM is a standalone academic field (Wynstra et al., 2019). They labelled Operations Management, Marketing and Strategy & Organization as what they called reference disciplines and keeping this perspective, they conducted a review of 2522 PSM publications appeared in some dozen and a half high-impact management journals published between 1995 to 2014 (Wynstra et al., 2019). They concluded after evaluating those publications how PSM research had been developing over time in terms of numbers, content, topics and the theories addressed and embedded in those published articles. They discovered conclusive evidences of diversity in terms of research topics and theories surrounding those three disciplines yet with considerable overlap when one looks at all of them in their totality; hence they concluded that the field is better represented by Latin proverb, "unity in diversity." (Wynstra et al., 2019).

We intentionally presented our representative literature review, which is by means exhaustive, in somewhat a chronological style as we wanted to show our reluctant colleagues and gate-keepers of these research in Pakistan that quantitative content analysis or alternatively summary count method as it is sometimes called is a viable tool for describing the state of the art of any developing field during its formative years. All above-mentioned studies had used it or its numerous variants to highlight trends or missed opportunities in fields as diverse as music, neurosurgery, business, purchasing, nursing, social marketing and event studies. It is obvious many studies in several emerging fields have been using abstract analysis or quantitative content analysis of entire theses/dissertations to figure out the trends in the field as well as to make valid judgments on the quality of the research work produced. Likewise, research in Business Administration and Management Sciences is an emerging and evolving field in the context of Pakistan.

Furthermore, as stated earlier, the importance and relevance of abstracts could hardly be overestimated as often it is the part of the thesis or other research work, which is used by various data-bases for retrieval purposes. Consequently, there is a growing trend led by journals and data-bases towards standardization of abstracts. Therefore, we believe one could make some limited yet valid judgments regarding the PhD theses/dissertations in Business Administration and Management Sciences currently being produced in Pakistan by evaluating only their abstracts and some allied contextual data. At least, seven studies cited above made use of abstract analysis almost exclusively, however we extracted and inferred 4 data categories from theses as well like many other studies cited above. Nevertheless, we relied heavily on abstract analysis as a primary source of our data input as 10 data categories were constructed out of abstracts. Nevertheless, 3 categories of researcher's attribute and 7 contextual categories of data were also extracted.

Methodology

Meta-analysis, a research technique dates back late 60s but made famous once Glass explained it in his famous work in mid-70s. In a meta-analysis study, researchers employ statistical procedures using effectsized data to establish the comparative findings from all disparate researches to be eventually synthesized and presented for the meta-study (Glass, 1976). Over time, meta-analysis evolved in various variants and one such variant research technique arising out of communication studies is content analysis. Researchers in the field of communication have been using content analysis to quantitatively isolate and categorize data within the content of communication, whether by text, speech, images, or video (Krippendorff, 2004).

In the content analysis, initially preset can be implemented deductively on the basis of previous literature (Neuendorf, 2016); however often new categories emerge from data inductively once researchers start dissecting data. Theses/dissertations research produced in universities under the framework of doctoral programs does represent emerging trends in an academic field or discipline, therefore no wonder several newer studies could be cited where researchers deployed content analysis for dissecting dissertations in fields as diverse as rehabilitation counseling (Zanskas, Phillips, Tansey, & Smith, 2013); which was in fact third such study in the field as two prior ones covered period from 2005 to 2007 (Tansey, Zanskas & Phillips, 2011), and 2008 to 2010 (Tansey, Phillips & Zanskas, 2012). Another examples are study on business ethics (Piotrowski & Guyette, 2014), cooperative learning (Dirlikli & Akgun, 2016), and the nexus between social media and education (Piotrowski, 2015).

This study utilizes content analysis as its research technique to examine a sample 96 dissertations' abstracts found by searching digital database of Pakistan Higher Education Commission's Repository for dissertations produced in the field of Business Administration and Management Sciences from 1990 through 2017.

The overarching research question for this study was: What can we learn by evaluating Business Administration and Management Sciences doctoral dissertations' abstracts and some allied categories of contextual data and data from these themselves? We formulated the following three sub-questions: Who is doing the research and what is the context of research? What are some of the objective attributes of these being produced? What can we learn by doing content analysis of abstract section of those theses?

Afterwards, we elaborated and operationalized those questions by creating specific objective categories of data, which would help us in answering those questions. For instance, to answer the first sub-question, we thought what are some of the objective facts regarding the researchers and research context like researchers' name, gender, universities they were enrolled in, cities where those universities were located, public or private status of their universities, the year they completed their thesis, and the topics of the researches? Finally, we looked into the context of research by describing the institutional structures, where those researches were produced and we further looked into the underlying disciplines of those researches.

In order to answer the second research question, we will make an attempt to collect data on categories like thesis type, format, length of the thesis and number of chapters a thesis contained by casually perusing through our sampled set of theses.

Finally, we created following 10 categories to answer the third research question: word count of abstracts, structure of abstracts in terms of number of paragraphs, research paradigm, research approach, research design, sector of economy where research was conducted, sources of data, data collection methods, data analysis techniques and whether abstracts discussed results and findings or not?

Findings and Discussion

The findings provide an overview of doctoral research related to Business Administration and Management Sciences' education. In our sample, there were 14 public universities contributed some 53 theses, while 9 private universities contributed 43 theses for a total of some 96 theses completed between 2008 to 2017. In the entire decade, 2009 turned out to be the most prolific year contributing some 23 theses to the list followed by 16 and 11 in 2012 and 2010 respectively. See Table # 1 in Appendix.

There were huge variations in theses' size with a length of 63 pages being the shortest thesis, while 520 pages long thesis being the longest one with an average length of approximately 250 pages (HEC., 2019). Similar fluctuations in abstracts structure were found as some were composed in one paragraph while the longest one had 11 paragraphs. The shortest abstract was only 169 words long, and the longest one had 904 words with an average of word count of 386 for an abstract. Out of 96 theses only 16 were written by female researchers and Islamabad happened to be the most productive city as it produced 67 theses followed by a distant Lahore with single digit score of 9 theses for the decade we studied.

Almost all of these were monograph and they were in the typical Introduction, Literature Review, Methodology, Discussion & Results (ILrMDR) five-chapter format, though the labelling of chapters varied from anywhere from 1 to 14. Likewise, almost all theses had positivism as their research philosophy except one adhering to interpretivism. In the same vein, almost the entire sample data-set relied on deductive research approach except one odd exception, while theses' research designs were pre-dominantly quantitative (HEC., 2019). Furthermore, the overwhelming majority theses relied on respondents followed by some studies collected data from informants and there were 15 abstracts, which did not even discuss results and findings. Such a monotonous structural adherence to one blue print for success betray the risk averse position of researchers and their herd mentality. No wonder allegations are mounting that research produced in country is without social relevance and academic significance.

We discovered a lot of variation, however in the context of research as defined by us based on literature:

Table # 2

Context of Research [Administrative units within universities, where researches were produced]

Faculty of Advanced Integrated Studies & Research	25
Department of Business Administration	3
Department of Engineering	1
Department of Engineering Management	2
Department of Law & Management Studies	2
Department of Administrative Studies	1
Engineering and Management Sciences	5
Engineering and Technology	3
Institute of Administrative Sciences	1

Management & Social Sciences	14
Management Sciences	33
Public Administration	1
School of Business	1
School of Management	1

It seems research producing universities have organized their Business Administration and Management Sciences research producing units in various administrative, departments, inter-departmental units, institutes, schools, faculties and inter-faculties arrangements. It was beyond the scope of this research to figure out the impact of those administrative structural elements on actual research being produced. Moreover, it is not clear either whether Pakistani universities follow international norms in structuring their internal organization or such differences and consequent designations like school of business, department of business or labelling of an administrative unit as institute are the results of historical preferences of people in-charge then.

We observed a somewhat restricted variety in data collection methods with survey being the method of choice. It was followed by interviews, secondary data, observations, field data, document analysis and one exceptional study did claim to have used experimental design.

Data analysis part had all the usual suspects with some finer elements as well; however quantitative side dominated the analysis section for obvious reasons:

Table # 3

Type of Statistical Analysis

Quantitative	Qualitative
Regress (linear, multiple, moderated, step-wise)	Content Analysis
Correlation	Phenomenology
Factor Analysis (Explanatory, Confirmatory)	
Path Analysis	
PLS	
Anova& Manova	
SEM, SEM Bootstrapping	
OLS estimation	
T-test	
Sobel test	
Post Hoc LSD Hayes macro process	
Chi Square	
Preacher, Rucker, Hayes moderation macro	

Corporate world dominated as the desired sector for data collection followed by higher education, banking and public sector respectively. Altogether there were only 21 separate sectors, where those theses research were conducted.

Table # 4

Sectors [where researches were conducted]

Banking	9
Civil Servants (Balochistan)	2
Corporate	40
Nursing	2
Energy Sector (Oil Companies)	2
Financial Sector	2
Higher Education (IT, Pharmacy, Public Sector)	10
Industrial Workers & Labor Unions	2
IT	1
NGO	1
Pharma (Companies and Sector)	2
Power Distribution	1
Professionals (Medical Doctors)	1

Project Management	2
Public Sector	8
Quality	1
Regularity Authority	1
Service Sector	2
SMEs	3
Telecom	2
Textile	2

Almost a whopping 75 percent of these researches belonged to various specialty areas of HRM/OB, betraying the tried and tested nature of these research. The interdisciplinary field of leadership and these under the rubric of quality tied together as 5 studies each were found for these topics.

Table # 5

Underlying discipline of theses/dissertations

HRM/OB	73
CSR/Ethics	2
Emotional Intelligence	2
Entrepreneurship & Partnership	3
Leadership	5
Governance	2
Industrial Management	2
Organizational learning	1
Public Administration	2
Quality Management and Total Quality Management	5
Technology Adoption	1

In short, a typical thesis in Business Administration and Management Sciences is likely to be formulaic monograph, written by a male, in a five chapter format spread over approximately 250 pages, adhering to positivism research philosophy, deductive in its approach, quantitative in its methodology, using an adapted survey instrument to collect data from corporate respondents, while relying on descriptive stats, correlation and regression as its data analysis techniques to arrive at some mundane findings and recommendations.

Future Research & Implications

This research focused on extracted quantitative data through content analysis primarily from abstract section of theses of Business Administration and Management Sciences theses and some allied contextual categories of those theses. In future, the relationship and impact of research context could be explored to see if structural composition of places of research has any impact on the quality and variety of the research produced in those centers. Researchers could focus on some more data categories like guiding frameworks in those theses, thesis aspects like what are the publication ratios etc. or whether data was collected through an established instrument or test inventory. Further research could be done to see if theories are embedded in Business Administration and Management Sciences research and or what are some of the important theories utilized by these writers in Pakistan. The frequency, prevalence and quality of statistical analysis could also be charted by researchers in any future endeavors. In fact, for a more comprehensive study like the several studies cited in our literature review content analysis could be used on entire theses instead of just their abstract sections.

Recommendations

Given the variation in the length, structure and the information contained in a typical abstract, the HEC should either provide concrete guidelines or must adopt some standardized abstract format like Ansio 10 ANSI/NISO Z39.14 (R2015) (Niso, 2019) to highlight the importance of abstract in a thesis as currently it seems researchers do not even have rudimentary knowledge as to what elements to be included in an abstract. The HEC has successfully implemented the requirement of a Turnitin similarity test to discourage plagiarism and there is no reason to believe that if the above suggestion will be implemented by the HEC, the researchers, their supervisors, the program managers, the examiners, the committee members and the institutions will not heed its advice.

The HEC and relevant universities and concerned stakeholders like program managers, supervisors, examiners, curriculum developers, evaluators and thesis committees should start looking into those structural and academic elements, which are constraining variety, vitality, risk-taking and ingenuity in Business Administration and Management Sciences theses/dissertation research in Pakistan; a fact extrapolated by our limited findings. Finally, the gatekeepers: supervisors, examiners, evaluators and thesis committees, must encourage and facilitate risk taking in structuring thesis research and demand some real contextual relevance for the selection of topics henceforth.

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